

Article:

Cu₃TaTe₄: Synthesis, X-ray Diffraction, Scanning Electron Microscopy, and Diffuse Reflectance Measurements

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Abstract

In the present investigation Polycrystalline samples of Cu₃TaTe₄ were prepared by the melt and anneal method. X-Ray Diffraction (*XRD*) and Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (*DRS*) measurements were performed to verify the crystal structure and calculate the indirect and direct band gaps. The results showed a lattice parameter $a = 5.9082 \text{ \AA}$, a stoichiometry with a Ta deficit of 17.8 %, indirect bandgap $E_g^i = 0.38 \text{ eV}$, and a direct gap $E_g^d = 2.38 \text{ eV}$. The analyzes confirm that Cu₃TaTe₄ can be used as an *p*-type absorbent for thin film solar cells with the advantages that its elements have low toxicity and have lower costs than those used today.

Key words: Cu₃TaTe₄; diffuse reflectance; optical bandgap.

Artículo:

Cu₃TaTe₄: Medidas de síntesis, difracción de rayos X, microscopía electrónica de barrido y reflectancia difusa

Resumen

En la presente investigación fueron preparadas muestras policristalinas de Cu₃TaTe₄ por el método de fusión y recocido. Se realizaron medidas de difracción de rayos X (*DRX*) y espectroscopía de reflectancia difusa (*ERD*) para verificar la estructura cristalina y calcular las brechas de energía directa e indirecta. Los resultados mostraron un parámetro de red $a = 5,9082 \text{ \AA}$, una estequiometría deficitaria en Ta del 17,8 %, una brecha de energía indirecta $E_g^i = 0,38 \text{ eV}$ y una brecha de energía directa $E_g^d = 2,38 \text{ eV}$. Los análisis confirman que el Cu₃TaTe₄ puede ser empleado como absorbente *p*-tipo para células solares de películas finas con las ventajas de que sus elementos presentan baja toxicidad y tienen costos menores a los empleados en la actualidad.

Palabras claves: Cu₃TaTe₄; reflectancia difusa; brecha óptica de energía.

1 Introduction

The sylvanite family of compounds, with chemical formula $\text{Cu}_3\text{-TM-VI}_4$, (TM is the transition metal V, Nb, or Ta and VI is S, Se, or Te), is composed of nine members; three sulfides: Cu_3VS_4 , Cu_3NbS_4 , Cu_3TaS_4 ; three selenides: Cu_3VSe_4 , Cu_3NbSe_4 , Cu_3TaSe_4 ; and three tellurides: Cu_3VTe_4 , Cu_3NbTe_4 , Cu_3TaTe_4 . They are all semiconductors. As-growth samples show *p*-type electrical conductivity, high ionic mobility, low hole effective mass, high optical absorption in the visible and UV range, and optical bandgaps suitable for their use as an absorber layer in thin-film solar photovoltaic devices [1, 2].

Sylvanites crystallize in the cubic structure, space group (N 215), consisting of Cu, TM and VI atoms located at the atom-sites (Wyckoff coordinates): 3d (0.5, 0, 0), 1a (0, 0, 0) and 4e (*u*, *u*, *u*), respectively (Figure 1) [3, 4, 5], described for the first time by Pauling and Hultgren [6] for the natural mineral, Cu_3VS_4 .

Figure 1: The unit cell of sylvanite Cu_3TaTe_4 . Image created using Diamond software version 3.2e with lattice parameter $a = 6.025 \text{ \AA}$ [7] and anion displacement $u = 0.2558$ [7]

Although this semiconductor family has been extensively studied by *ab initio* calculations [2]-[5], [7]-[17] experimental results are relatively scarce, in particular for Cu_3TaTe_4 . The experimental value of the lattice parameter *a* for Cu_3TaTe_4 has been reported by Hulliger [18], Zitter *et al.* [19], and Li *et al.* [20] as 5.928 Å, 5.9283 Å, and 5.930(2) Å, respectively; in good agreement with theoretical calculations of Hong *et al.* (6.01 Å) [13] and Kehoe

et al. (5.906 Å) [2], (6.033 Å) [9]. No experimental data for optical properties, as the bandgap (E_g), were found in the literature.

In this work, the measurement of the bandgap value for Cu_3TaTe_4 is reported for the first time. The bandgap is essential for applications in optoelectronic devices as light detectors and solar cells.

2 Experimental procedure

2.1 Synthesis

Polycrystalline samples of Cu_3TaTe_4 have been produced by the melt and anneal method as is described below. Starting materials (Cu, Ta, and Te) with nominal purity of 99.99 wt. % in the stoichiometric ratio were mixed in an evacuated (10^{-4} Torr) and sealed the quartz tube with the inner walls previously carbonized to prevent the chemical reaction of the elements with quartz. The quartz ampoule is heated until 723 K (melting point of Te) keeping this temperature for 48 h and shaking all the time using an electromechanical motor. This procedure guarantees the formation of binary species at low temperatures avoiding the existence of free Te at high temperatures, which could produce Te deficiency in the ingot. Then the temperature was slowly increased until 1423 K, with the mechanical shaker always connected for better mixing of the components. After 24 h, the cooling cycle begins until the anneal temperature (800 K) with the mechanical shaker is disconnected. The ampoule is keeping at the annealing temperature for 30 days to assure thermal equilibrium. Then the furnace is switching off, letting naturally cooling the ampoule to room temperature.

2.2 X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

X-ray powder diffraction data were collected employing a diffractometer (Siemens D5005) equipped with a graphite monochromator ($\text{CuK}\alpha$ $\lambda = 1.54059 \text{ \AA}$) at 40 kV and 20 mA. Silicon powder was used as an external standard. The samples were scanned from $10 - 100^\circ 2\theta$, with a step size of 0.02° and counting time of 20 s. The Bruker analytical software was used to establish the positions of

Figure 2: X-ray diffraction pattern of Cu_3TaTe_4 . The numbers over the peaks correspond to the hkl-Miller indices. Red asterisks signal two unidentified peaks

the peaks from the $\text{CuK}\alpha_1$ component and to strip mathematically the $\text{CuK}\alpha_2$ components from each reflection. The peak positions were extracted employing a single-peak profile fitting carried out through the Bruker DIFFRAC^{plus} software. Each reflection was modeled utilizing a pseudo-Voigt function.

2.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

Stoichiometric relations were investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique, using Hitachi S2500 equipment. The microchemical composition was found by an energy-dispersive x-ray spectrometer (EDS) coupled with a computer-based multichannel analyzer (MCA, Delta III analysis, and Quantex software, Kevex). For the EDS analysis, $\text{K}\alpha$ lines were used. The accelerating voltage was 15 kV. The samples were tilted 35 degrees. A standardless EDS analysis was made with a relative error of $\pm(5-10)\%$ and detection limits of the order of 0.3 wt %, where the k-ratios are based on theoretical standards.

2.4 Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (DRS)

Optical absorbance has been measured in the energy range 0.5 to 6 eV using Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (DRS) technique using a UV-Visible-IR spectrophotometer equipped with a diffuse reflectance accessory (integrating sphere) capable of collecting the reflected flux. The sample was ground in an agate mortar to obtain a fine powder ($< 10 \mu\text{m}$). Barium sulfate (Merck DIN 5033) was used as an internal standard.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 X-ray diffraction

Figure 2 shown the X-ray diffraction pattern. Using DIVOL06 software [21] the lattice parameter has been calculated as $a = 5.9082 \text{ \AA}$ in good agreement with previous reports [22]. Traces of a secondary phase, signaled by red asterisks in Figure 2, are also observed; however, this phase cannot be unambiguously identified with the present information.

Table 1: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) results for Cu_3TaTe_4

	Weight Concentration %			Atom Concentration %		
	Cu	Ta	Te	Cu	Ta	Te
Cu_3TaTe_4 .pt1	23.35 ± 0.52	10.06 ± 0.25	66.59 ± 0.70	36.83 ± 0.83	10.85 ± 0.26	52.32 ± 0.55
Cu_3TaTe_4 .pt2	23.19 ± 0.54	9.90 ± 0.25	66.91 ± 0.72	36.65 ± 0.85	10.70 ± 0.27	52.65 ± 0.57
Cu_3TaTe_4 .pt3	24.31 ± 0.56	8.94 ± 0.23	66.76 ± 0.72	38.18 ± 0.88	9.60 ± 0.25	52.22 ± 0.57
Cu_3TaTe_4 .pt4	23.48 ± 0.56	9.69 ± 0.17	66.83 ± 0.73	37.04 ± 0.88	10.45 ± 0.18	52.51 ± 0.58
Cu_3TaTe_4 .pt5	23.05 ± 0.56	8.98 ± 0.16	67.97 ± 0.74	36.56 ± 0.88	9.75 ± 0.18	53.69 ± 0.58
Mean values	23.48	9.51	67.01	37.05	10.27	52.68

3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

To verify the stoichiometry SEM measurements were performed. Figure 3 display the corresponding microphotography, indicating the five (5) points where the experimental stoichiometry was measured. Table 1 present the obtained values. The calculated nominal stoichiometry of Cu_3TaTe_4 , in atom concentration, is Cu = 37.5 %, Ta = 12.5 %, and Te = 50.0 %; the porcentual deviations with respect to the mean experimental values are Cu = 1.2 %, Ta = 17.8 % and Te = 5.4 %.

Figure 3: Microphotography of Cu_3TaTe_4 . The numbers signal the points where the stoichiometry was measured in correspondense with Table 1

3.3 Diffuse reflectance

The optical absorption of Cu_3TaTe_4 was measured at ambient conditions using the diffuse reflectance technique [23] where the reflectance $F(R_\infty)$ is given by the Equation (1)

$$\frac{K}{S} = \frac{(1 - R_\infty)^2}{2R_\infty} = F(R_\infty), \quad (1)$$

K and S are the absorption and scattering coefficients of the sample, respectively; R_∞ is the reflectance, and $F(R_\infty)$ is usually termed the remission or Kubelka-Munk (K-M) function. Figure 4 show the (K-M) function for Cu_3TaTe_4 .

Figure 4: Experimental absorbance for Cu_3TaTe_4 . The numbers correspond to the energies of the absorption bands

The experimental absorbance of Cu_3TaTe_4 in the energy interval $1 < E(\text{eV}) < 6$ shows several structures or energy bands that, in the absence of other experimental results, can be compared with calculations of Kehoe *et al.* [2], Ali *et al.* [7] and Espinoza *et al.* [8]. It is founding a relatively good agreement because the off-stoichiometric character of real samples is not properly represented in theoretical studies. It was postulated that intrinsic defects within the material affect the bandgap as measured by optical spectroscopy, something

that can be accounted for if excitonic effects were considered [1].

Concerning the energy gap, it is accepted that fundamental band gaps of all sulvanites are naturally indirect [9] because the conduction band minimum (CBM) is located at X point of the Brillouin Zone (BZ) while the valence band maximum (VBM) is located at R point of the BZ [7]. In consequence, indirect transitions are $R \rightarrow X$ type, whereas direct transitions (if they are not forbidden) are at X point.

Figure 5: Absorbance (left), indirect (center), and direct (right) optical energy gaps of Cu_3TaTe_4

In Figure 5, using the absorption of Figure 4 and Tauc's plot method [24], direct (X) and indirect ($R \rightarrow X$) transitions values have been obtained founding $E_g^i = 0.38$ eV and $E_g^d = 2.39$ eV. The E_g^i results too much lower than those calculated theoretically. Usually, theoretical calculations produce values that are lower than experimental [7] in consequence the disagreement must become from the polycrystalline character of the sample. The fingerprint of cationic disorder is the broad shoulder in the direct gap curve of Figure 5. Defect states and phonon absorption produce an additional optical absorption at energies a little lower than the bandgap.

The direct gap E_g^d value is higher than those calculated as usually happens. However, the curve of E_g^d fits very well with Tauc's method clearly showing an absorption front. The bandgap of sulvanites increases with the atomic number of the chalcogen atom (S, Se, Te); and effectively, comparing the direct bandgap of Cu_3TaTe_4 (2.39 eV) (this work), Cu_3TaSe_4 (2.43 eV) [22], and Cu_3TaS_4 (2.76 eV) [25], value of the present work accomplished the empirical rule.

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Table 2: Comparative bandgaps values for Cu_3TaTe_4

E_g^i [eV]	E_g^d [eV]	Reference
1.11	1.69	Kahoe <i>et al.</i> [2]
1.112, 1.837, 0.972		Ali <i>et al.</i> [7]
1.171, 1.323		Hong <i>et al.</i> [13]
0.38	2.39	This work

In Table 2, the experimental values are compared with previous calculations.

4 Conclusion

Cu_3TaTe_4 has been synthesized by the melt-anneal method and characterized by DRX, SEM, and Diffuse Absorption. DRX and SEM show a polycrystalline sample with $a = 5.9082$ Å in agreement with previous reports and a stoichiometric deficit of Ta (17.8 %). The indirect and direct bandgaps were measured as $E_g^i = 0.38$ eV and $E_g^d = 2.39$ eV, respectively. These results confirm that Cu_3TaTe_4 may be a good candidate as p -type absorber material for thin-film solar cells with the advantages that their elements are not so toxic as Cd, less expensive than Ga, and more abundant than the rare In, materials that are extensively used in the actuality. Also, it can be used with window materials, as CdS with a lattice mismatch of only 1.53 %.

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